

Performance Measurement Using the Human Resources Scorecard (HRSC) Method at Fishing Industry in Kendari

Lamatinulu¹, Irma Nur Afiah², Kardenia Faisal³

^{1,2,3}Department of Industrial Engineering, Faculty of Industrial Technology
Universitas Muslim Indonesia Makassar, Indonesia

Corresponding Author: Lamatinulu

Abstract:- In the face of increasingly rapid economic growth, companies must maximize their overall performance. Companies can utilize resources effectively and efficiently so that the company can achieve its vision and mission. The research used the Human Resources Scorecard (HRSC) approach combined with the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) method. The HRSC method is used to measure the performance of Human Resources (HR) in terms of financial, customer, internal business and learning and growth perspectives. From the four perspectives, eight key performance indicators (KPIs) are obtained. The measurement results with the HRSC method approach found that the performance of the financial aspect was in the very good category with a score of 5, the customer aspect was in the good performance category with a score of 4. The internal business process aspect obtained good category performance with a weight of 4.2. The performance of the growth and learning aspects is in the very good category with a value of 4.83. Overall, the results of the analysis of human resource performance measurements using the HRSC approach show a weight value of 4.64 which means that the performance of human resources in fishing industry companies is very good.

Keywords:- Performance Measurement, Human Resources Scorecard.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of the world economy demands competition between companies to maximize their overall performance. In facing this competition, companies can utilize resources effectively and efficiently so that the company's vision and mission can be achieved. One strategy that can be implemented is to improve the performance of available human resources. Carrying out activities to achieve predetermined goals requires various factors of production, such as labor, raw materials, capital, and expertise. In this case, labor or employees are human resources that are very valuable to a company. A trained workforce plays an important role in realizing or achieving company goals. Therefore, human resources in the company must be managed properly so that it can run smoothly. Human resources should be a source of added value (value-adding) for the organization, where the company's performance measurement and assessment must continue to be developed to support the company's strategy. HRSC is a way to link

human resource strategy with corporate strategy to achieve good company performance [1, 2, 3, 4]. PT. Sultratuna Samudera Kendari is one of the companies in the fishing industry that was built in 1990 and began operating in 1992. It is located within the Kendari Ocean Fishing Port (PPS Kendari) area. The company has several departments, namely reception, production, packing, and export departments. To determine the performance of employees, especially those in the production department. After initial observations, problems were found in the company, such as decreased performance of employees in the production section, one of which was when doing weddings was not thorough and when metal checks there were fishing rods so that the octopus had to be processed from the initial stage, which had an impact on employee productivity targets.

To solve performance problems, it is necessary to measure the performance of human resources using the HRSC method combined with the AHP method so that it is known what indicators need to be improved or repaired and that it is expected creating competitive strategy steps to achieve sustainable performance improvement in the future. The methods used in this study are the HRSC method and the AHP method. To produce a superior company, it is necessary to measure the performance of human resources such as the HRSC method which can link people, strategy and performance. Measurable vision, strategy and contribution of human resources can be described by the HRSC method. Something that intangible into tangible can be explained by the HRSC method [5].

The performance indicators obtained are then weighted using pairwise comparison cards using the AHP method. AHP is a weighting method introduced by Thomas L. Saaty. To get the value of the performance measurement weight used the AHP method. Determination of the weight is based on the preferences of decision makers on the value of the importance of performance indicators. In the AHP analysis, the weight value meets the consistent criteria if the consistency ratio value is less than or equal to 0.1. [6].

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this research is a combination of HRSC and AHP. AHP is a decision-making approach designed to help solve complex problems with multiple criteria in various application areas. AHP is a method designed for decision making and solving complex problems by considering several criteria. This method is effective and practical for complex decisions that require the qualitative and quantitative aspects to align. AHP helps decision-makers organize important components of a problem in a hierarchical structure. The steps for calculating the weight in AHP are as follows [6]:

- Create a decision hierarchy structure
- Make a paired matrix
- Perform pairwise comparisons
- Determine the weight of each criterion
- Calculating the eigenvalues by squaring the matrix, calculating the sum of the values from each row, then normalizing; stopping this process if the difference between the sums of two consecutive calculations is less than a certain limit value.
- Calculating the consistency index (CI) to determine the consistency of answers that will affect the validity of the results with the formula:

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where CI is the symbol for Consistency Index, λ_{max} is the symbol for Eigenvalues, and n is the symbol for many alternatives.

The determination of the consistency vector is based on the average value of the vector sum weight. The weight value is calculated by multiplying the two pairwise comparison matrices. The consistency ratio is calculated to find out whether CI of a certain size is good enough or not. The consistency ratio that is considered good is CR 0.1. The CR formula is:

$$CR = CI/RI \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where: CR = Consistency ratio; RI = Ratio Index; CI = Consistency Index.

Where RI is a random index value issued by Oakridge Laboratory. The software used in this research is the Expert Choice software. Expert choice software is software that supports collaborative decision-making and a hardware system that enables groups to make decisions that are more efficient, analytical, and justifiable. Enables real-time interaction of the management team to reach a consensus on a decision. The method used in the use of expert choice software is the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) method. The steps in the research process are described below:

A. Identification Stage

At this stage it starts with problem identification and is followed up with problem formulation. The problem in this study is to determine the requirements for measuring the performance of human resources in the production section of

the fishing industry in the city of Kendari, Southeast Sulawesi.

B. Design Stage

The design stage in this study is to design a human resource performance measurement mechanism based on HRSC with the following stages:

- *Define business strategy clearly*
Defining performance measurement on each perspective that will be measured by translating the company's vision, mission, policies and strategies into strategic goals.
- *Building a business case for HR, where HR is a strategic asset of the company.*
The problem of human resources is how the company can be maintained by the company's employees through performance improvement to realize employee satisfaction.
- *Creating a corporate strategy map*
The company's strategy map is graphically sourced from the value chain. This is related to the representation that shows how human resources work together to create added value and accommodate the role of employees.
- *Define HR deliverables in the strategy map*
The next step is to define a strategy map where fishing industry companies in Kendari can make a real contribution to implementing business strategies.

➤ *Align HR Architecture and HR Deliverables*

The process that needs to be done at this step is to understand what is needed and what needs to be done to show how to form a good alignment between the HR system and strategy implementation so as to produce the HR deliverable. In this step, understanding the needs that need to be carried out in establishing alignment of the HR system and implementing strategies that produce HR with high performance. After the relationship between HR architecture and HR availability has been determined, an HR performance measurement system is designed and the HR performance measurement system scorecard is designed.

C. Measurement Stage

At the HR performance measurement stage, weighting is carried out based on actual data and targets set in performance measurement. This is done by determining the achievement score of HR performance with a Likert scale.

- The weighting process is carried out using the AHP method to determine the level of importance of the strategic objectives of each perspective. The AHP analysis weighting value is used to calculate the performance achievement score.
- The score for achieving strategic performance objectives is the result of multiplying the weight value by the score for each strategic objective. The achievement score for each perspective is obtained from the total weight multiplied by the strategic goal score. The overall HR performance score is obtained by multiplying the total weight by the performance achievement score.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Strategic Objectives must be carried out first for each perspective, and then Key Performance Indicators are determined for each perspective.

A. Financial Perspective

From a financial perspective, with the Human Resources Scorecard approach, the strategy applied is organizational development and its supporting human resource infrastructure. The objective applied by the company from a financial perspective is to improve the performance of human resources through optimizing employee training costs (effective training at efficient costs) and efficiency in employee recruitment costs.

- *Strategic objectives from a financial perspective are:*
 - Improving human resource performance capabilities to meet global competition
 - Conduct cost effectiveness by conducting cost efficiency and recruitment cost efficiency (RCE) training.
- *Key performance indicators to be achieved are:*
 - Outcome Measure: Training Cost Efficiency and Recruitment Cost Efficiency.
 - Performance Driver Measure: Efficiency of company expenses.
 - Target: training cost efficiency (TCE) of 4% and recruitment cost efficiency (RCE) of 5%.
- *Strategic Initiative:*
 - Organize optimal training (intensive, effective, and efficient) with minimal costs according to company needs.
 - Selection of employees who will take part in training as needed
 - Recruitment of employees as needed and prioritized from within the company itself

B. Customer Perspective

From the perspective of the customer, with the Human Resources Scorecard approach, the customers are employees of PT. Southeast Sulawesi Samudra Kendari. Performance measurement from a customer's (employee's) perspective with the HRSC approach is carried out to determine the image and reputation of PT. Sultratuna Samudra Kendari in the eyes of its employees.

- *The strategic objectives from a customer perspective are:*
 - Increase employee satisfaction at work.
 - Reducing employee turnover at the company
 - Suppressing the level of employee absenteeism in the company by establishing good cooperation between employees, as well as with superiors and subordinates.
- *Key performance indicators to be achieved are:*
 - Outcomes Measure: Employee Turnover (employee turnover), Employee Absenteeism (employee attendance), and Employee Satisfaction (employee satisfaction).

- Performance Driver Measure: Reducing Employee Turnover; increasing employee awareness of work responsibilities; and meeting the needs of employees according to the company's capabilities.

➤ *Target:*

- Employee Turnover Below 3%, Employee Absenteeism Below 1%, and Employee Satisfaction Index (ESI) The total score reaches 2100 points.

➤ *Strategic Initiative:*

- Creating conducive working conditions.
- Provide good facilities for employees.
- Provide appropriate remuneration with periodic salary increases based on company policy.

C. Internal business process perspective

In this perspective, so that there is no decrease in human resource performance, the company must always control the progress of its employees. One of them is by holding coordination meetings for employees regularly with the aim that the company is always consistent with effective and efficient principles. On the other hand, good cooperation from superiors and subordinates will create a pleasant atmosphere at work and is expected to increase the sense of responsibility for employees.

➤ *Strategic objectives from the perspective of internal business processes are:*

- Improving the quality of human resources by providing coordination meetings between leaders and staff so that the progress of employees can be monitored.
- Increase employee productivity.

➤ *The KPIs to be achieved are:*

- Outcomes Measure: average coordination time between superiors and staff; and employee productivity levels.
- Performance Driver Measure: Control the progress and abilities of employees
- Target: average coordination time of 96 hours per year, productivity employee 80%
- Strategic Initiatives:
 - ✓ Hold coordination meetings continuously
 - ✓ Improve discipline with frequent inspections.

D. Learning and Growth Perspective

The learning and growth perspective is measured based on the increase in the number of competent employees as well as the number of training and development programs held for employees. In operating this process, the company needs productive employees. The purpose of this perspective is to increase the competence of each employee to achieve the goals of the company's organization.

- The strategic objectives in this perspective are improving competency by exploring the potential of each employee. Improving employee competence with training and development.
- The KPIs to be achieved are:
 - ✓ Outcome Measure: Mastery of skills (expertise and ability) of employees in their respective fields.

- ✓ Performance Driver Measure: Controlling the skills and abilities of employees periodically and providing the type of training needed to improve employee skills
- ✓ The target number of employees who are competent in their field reaches 75%, and the type of training according to the needs of each employee is carried out for an average of 10 working days a year
- ✓ Strategic Initiative: exploring potential and empowering employees at optimal performance levels and always providing up-to-date knowledge or information to employees according to their field of work

E. Results of the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)

In this study, AHP was used as a decision-making tool. The weighting will be considered consistent if the IR value is <0.1 ($\leq 10\%$), then the AHP weighting value can be used as the criterion weighting value.

F. Value perspective in HRSC

Based on the results of the AHP analysis, the weight values obtained from the 4 priority perspectives of Human Resources performance need to be analyzed as shown in Figure 1.

Synthesis with respect to: Goal: Human Resources Scorecard

Fig. 1: Value of each Perspective

The IR value shows 0.03, so the perspective value in HRSC can be said to be consistent.

G. Assess each HRSC perspective

The results of the assessment of each HRSC perspective using AHP analysis are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: The results of the assessment HRSC perspective

Perspective	Key Performance Indicators (KPI)	Code	Weight Value
Financial	Training cost	F1	0.750
	Recruitment Costs	F2	0.250
Customer	Employee turnover	C1	0.493
	Employee presence	C2	0.311
	Employee satisfaction	C3	0.196
Internal Business Process	Coordination of superiors and staff	I1	0.200
	Employee productivity	I2	0.800
Learning and Growth	Employee expertise	L1	0.833
	Education and training	L2	0.167

The results of determining the weight values in Table 1 can be accepted and used because the IR value is <0.1.

H. Results of Human Resource Performance Measurement for Each Perspective

Measurement of human resource performance with the HRSC approach to four perspectives, namely the perspective of Financial, Customer, Internal, Business Process, Learning, and Growth is carried out comprehensively. The purpose of measuring the performance of human resources in each HRSC perspective is the actualization of the

company's strategy which is a benchmark for achieving company goals, targets, and assessments that provide direction towards success.

Table 2: Target and Performance for each KPI

Perspective	KPI	Target 2021	Performance 2021	Weight
Financial Perspective	F1	4% efficiency	4% efficiency	STT
	F2	5% efficiency	5% efficiency	STT
Customer Perspective	C1	≤3%	2,5%	STT
	C2	1%	1%	STT
	C3	2.100	1.675	NRT
Internal Business Process	I1	96 hours/year	100 hours/year	STT
	I2	80%	80%	STT
Learning Growth Perspective	L1	Average 10 working days per year	Average 10 working days per year	STT
	L2	≥75%	80%	STT

Note Description: STT=Successfully hit the target; NRT= Not yet reached Target

I. HR Performance Measurement Based on HRSC

In the total measurement of HR performance, the evaluation criteria are determined based on the score. The difference between the largest score and the smallest score is

divided by the number of classes, namely 5 so that a value of 0.03 is obtained. The total category of performance measurement is as follows:

Table 3: Total HR Performance Measurement Categories

Grouping of Measurement Results	Employee Performance Category
1.0 ≤ measurement result < 1.8	Is very lacking
1.8 ≤ measurement results < 2.6	Is lacking
2.6 ≤ measurement result < 3.4	Moderate
3.4 ≤ measurement results < 4.2	Good
4.2 ≤ measurement result < 5.0	Is very good

Source: Saaty (1993)

J. Financial Perspective

The results of measuring the performance of human resources in the fishing industry of PT. Sultratuna Samudra Kendari from a financial perspective, as shown in Table 4,

achieves a weighted total score of 5 which, based on the assessment category table, is included in the very good performance category.

Table 4: Financial Perspective Weighted Score

Perspective	2021		
	Score	Weighted	Weighted Score
Financial			
Training Cost	5	0,75	3,75
Recruitment Cost	5	0,25	1.25
Total			5

Source: Data Processed (2022)

K. Customer Perspective

The results of measuring the performance of human resources at PT. Sultratuna Samudra Kendari for the

customer perspective obtained a weighted total score of 4.49 which based on Table 5 the assessment category is in the very good performance category.

Table 5: Customer Perspective Weighted Score

Perspective	2021		
	Score	Weighted	Weighted Score
Customer			
Employee Turnover	5	0.49	2.45
Employee Presence	4	0,31	1.24
Employee Satisfaction		0.20	0.8
Total			4.49

Source: Data Processed (2022)

L. Internal Business Process Perspective

The results of HR performance measurement for the Internal Business Process perspective obtained a weighted

total score of 4.2 which based on Table 6 the assessment category is included in the good performance category.

Table 6: Weighted Scores from the Internal Business Process

Perspective	2021		
	Score	Weighted	Weighted Score
Internal Business Process	5	0,20	1
Coordination of superiors & staff	5	0,20	1
Employee Productivity	4	0.80	3.2
Total			4.2

Source: Data Processed (2022)

M. Learning and Growth Perspective

The results of measuring the performance of human resources for the Learning and Growth perspective reached a

total weighted score of 4.83, which based on the assessment category Table 7 was included in the very good performance category.

Table 7: Weighted Scores from Learning and Growth

Perspective	2021		
	Score	Weighted	Weighted Score
Learning and Growth	5	0.83	4.15
Skilled Employees	5	0.83	4.15
Training	4	0.17	0.68
Total			4.83

Source: Data Processed (2022)

N. Total performance measurement with HRSC approach

The results of measuring the performance of human resources at PT. Sultratuna Samudra Kendari achieved a

total weighted score of 4.64, the assessment category falling into the very good performance category.

Table 8: Total Performance Measurement using the Human Resource Scorecard approach

Perspective	2021		
	Score	Weighted	Weighted Score
Human Resource Scorecard	5	0.26	1.30
Financial	5	0.26	1.30
Customer	4.49	0.45	2.02
Internal Business Process	4.2	0.12	0.50
Learning and Growth	4.83	0.17	0.82
Total			4.64

Source: Data Processed (2022)

The financial perspective has a weight of 0.26, the customer perspective has a weight of 0.45, the internal business process perspective has a weight of 0.12, the learning and growth perspective has a weight of 0.17, is considered consistent because the IR value is smaller than 0.1. So that the results of the analysis with the AHP method can be used in analyzing the discussion of performance measurement.

The IR value is 0.03, which means that the AHP weighted value can be said to be consistent. It can be seen that high priority is given to the customer perspective, with a weighting of 0.45. This does not mean that other perspectives are ignored, because the four perspectives are interconnected. To be able to provide satisfaction to customers, management must first prioritize employee satisfaction because satisfied employees will provide satisfactory service to customers. The importance of employee satisfaction to performance. The aspect of employee satisfaction in carrying out work activities in the fishing industry is very important. This is consistent with research findings which state that employee achievement and performance are strongly influenced by employee job satisfaction [7]. The employee job satisfaction factor is also an important thing in motivating employees to work well in carrying out tasks so that it can have an impact on improving human resource performance in industrial companies [8].

From a financial perspective on training costs, the target of 4.5% has been achieved. Training costs incurred to optimize employee training activities carried out intensively, efficiently and effectively. Training cost from a financial perspective is considered optimal because it succeeds in achieving the target in line with the large number of trainings in the learning and growth perspective. From a financial perspective on training costs, we managed to achieve our target of 4.5%. Success can be achieved through the implementation of efficient and effective and appropriate training to improve employee skills. The cost of training from a financial perspective is considered optimal because it achieves the target along with a large of trainings from a learning, and growth perspective. The aspect of employee training in industrial organizations is very important because it is a very vital factor in optimizing employee performance [9, 10, 11]. It can also motivate employees to be more productive, efficient, and innovative at work. [12, 13].

Based on the results of the HR performance assessment related to Employee Turnover, a score of 5 is obtained with a weight of 0.49 so that a performance value of 2.45 is obtained. Related to the employee attendance indicator, the performance value is 1.24, while the employee satisfaction aspect is 0.8. The results of these findings indicate that the performance of Human Resources related to Employee Turnover greatly has an impact on performance.

Employee turnover is an important indicator for improving employee performance because employee turnover that is not properly controlled can have a negative impact on company profitability, competitiveness, and productivity [14, 15].

Based on the results of performance measurement from the perspective of internal business processes, it can be categorized as having good performance. In this perspective, the main performance indicator that can make a major contribution to employee performance is the level of productivity. Related to the performance indicators of employee productivity, it was found by previous researchers that it significantly influences industrial performance and is a very important factor for organizational performance [16, 17].

Based on the results of performance measurement from a learning and growth perspective, it can also be categorized as having good performance. In this perspective, the main performance indicator that can make a major contribution to employee performance is employee expertise with a weight value of 0.83. Employee performance is a function of several factors such as motivation and human resource skills. Employee skills needed to support performance are soft skills and hard skills. Both skills are needed because they can have a significant impact on employee performance [18, 19].

Based on the results of performance measurement from the perspective of internal business processes, it can be categorized as having good performance. In this perspective, the main performance indicator that can make a major contribution to employee performance is the level of productivity. Other research findings also further strengthen the argument that the performance of industrial organizations is strongly influenced by employee productivity. [20, 21]. The results of measuring the performance of human resources from the customer's perspective achieve a total weighted score of 4.49. which, based on the assessment category table, is included in the very good performance category. It is hoped that the company can continue to maintain performance from the customer's perspective. The results of measuring the performance of human resources from the perspective of business processes achieve a total weighted score of 4.2. based on the assessment category table, is included in the good performance category. Even though it has achieved a good performance target, the company still has to improve performance from the internal business process perspective so that in the coming year it can achieve a maximum performance score. The results of measuring the performance of human resources at PT. Sultratuna Samudra Kendari from the learning and growth perspective achieved a total weighted score of 4.83. which, based on the assessment category table, is included in the very good performance category. It is hoped that the company can maintain its performance from a learning and growth perspective.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This good performance is supported by the customer perspective, with a weighted score of 2.02, and the financial perspective, with a score of 1.30. While the learning and growth perspective has a weight of 0.12 and an internal business process perspective of 0.12. This shows that the fishing industry has shown very good resource performance, and it is hoped that the company can continue to maintain and even improve the performance of its resources to get the maximum performance score. It can be concluded that the performance of human resources at Fishing Industry in Kendari has been very good. And it is hoped that next year the performance of human resources can increase.

Based on the results and discussion above, it can be concluded that the performance at the fishing industry in Kendari can be measured using the Human Resource Scorecard method, which consists of four perspectives: a financial perspective, a customer perspective, an internal business process perspective, and a learning and growth perspective. Obtained measurement results from each perspective, namely the financial perspective with a weighted score of 5, included in the very good performance category. The customer perspective gets a weighted score of 4, included in the very good performance category. The internal business process perspective gets a weighted score of 4.2 in the good performance category. The learning and growth perspective, with a weighted score of 4.83, is included in the very good performance category. For the overall results of human resource performance based on the Human Resource Scorecard, a weighted score of 4.64 out of a maximum score of 5.00 means that the company's resource performance has achieved a very good human resource performance score from various perspectives.

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